

Photoelectrochemical Studies of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$

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Photoelectrochemical electrode of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ was prepared by standard ceramic technique. The electrode material was characterised by X-ray diffraction, electrical conductivity and diffuse reflectance spectroscopy. The photoelectrochemical properties of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ are reported. $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ seems to be a good choice as photoanode in PEC cell because of its 1.66 eV band gap. The conversion efficiency was found to be 0.127%.

In recent years, there has been intensive research in the field of photoelectrochemical (PEC) cells utilising semiconductor electrode junction¹. PEC cells are attracting a great deal of attention for their use in solar rechargeable batteries. However, they have been suffering by the relatively low conversion efficiency and poor stability offered by the semiconductor photoelectrode. Here we report our investigation on PEC conversion of solar energy using ternary oxide, $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ pellet, sintered in hydrogen atmosphere, as a semiconductor electrode.

Results and Discussion

The d -values for various plane and their relative intensities measured from the height of the peak in the diffractogram are given in Table 1. The compound is found to have tetragonal structure with lattice dimension as $a_0 = 9.8998 \text{ \AA}$, $b_0 = 8.1601 \text{ \AA}$. XRD pattern is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$

TABLE I—X-RAY DIFFRACTION RESULTS OF $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$

Symmetry : Tetragonal; Lattice parameters : $a_0 = 9.8998 \text{ \AA}$, $c_0 = 8.1601 \text{ \AA}$; Radiation: $\text{CuK}\alpha$

l/l_0	d_{obs}	d_{cal}	h	k	l	l/l_0	d_{obs}	d_{cal}	h	k	l
10.61	4.949	4.949	2	0	0	10.18	1.763	1.753	5	1	2
20.31	4.080	4.080	0	0	2	8.76	1.652	1.650	6	0	0
22.75	3.295	3.299	3	0	0	21.50	1.625	1.627	6	1	0
20.01	2.932	2.922	3	1	1	11.70	1.522	1.511	6	1	2
35.06	2.675	2.656	2	2	2	16.11	1.467	1.475	6	3	0
44.59	2.601	2.602	3	2	1	14.31	1.378	1.372	6	4	0
100.00	2.475	2.475	4	0	0	5.61	1.358	1.353	6	4	1
40.31	2.315	2.303	4	1	1	3.52	1.287	1.283	7	3	1
11.93	2.134	2.136	4	2	1	3.64	1.266	1.267	6	5	0
21.21	2.021	2.025	3	3	2	2.60	1.235	1.237	8	0	0
6.58	1.939	1.945	4	2	2	2.09	1.642	1.667	6	6	0
19.14	1.910	1.924	5	0	1	5.30	1.091	1.091	9	1	0

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The variation of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 2) is linear showing that well-known exponential law, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-Eg/KT)$ is obeyed in the temperature range covered. A break is found in the plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$ at 480 K when activation energy changes from 0.489 to 1.111 eV. The activation energy of conduction is found to be low for low temperature region. This low temperature

Fig. 2 Temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity of $YZn_2Cu_3O_{6.5}$.

conductivity can be attributed to extrinsic type of conduction, whereas the conduction in the higher temperature range may be regarded as intrinsic type². Conductivity of this material can be broadly explained as follows.

One of the major reasons of extrinsic conductivity for this compound may be due to the presence of other metals as impurity. $YZn_2Cu_3O_{6.5}$ prepared by this method may contain very small amount of other metals as impurity, since the oxide used were not of 'specpure' grade. Even a very small amount of impurity can drastically modify the electrical properties of semiconductor. At higher temperature these im-

purity atoms generally get ionised and do not show their effect.

Generally in the compounds containing transition metal ions, the electrical conduction is mostly characterised by d -band near the Fermi surface³. Due to the presence of d -band in transition metal ions two competing conduction processes can be identified: (i) conduction by hopping of charge carriers in the narrow $3d$ -band dominating at lower temperatures and (ii) normal band like conduction in $O^{2-} : 2P$ band which predominates in high temperature region and is able to suppress the conduction due to hopping. The change in conduction mechanism is indicated by the change in the slope of the plot of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$, and it may depend on the hopping energy involved, structural imperfections, impurity states and polaron formation. In the high temperature region, conductivity is predominantly due to $O^{2-} : 2P$ band conduction, which also involves filled and empty $3d$ -band. Graph also indicates that compound is semiconducting in nature⁴.

Hemispherical reflectance spectra (Fig. 3) were scanned using a Varian DMS 80 spectrophotometer⁵. The band gap was found to be 1.66 eV. The difference in the values of band gap and activation energy, determined from reflectance spectra and electrical conductivity measurement respectively, is attributed to different experimental conditions and the source of electron excitation.

Fig. 3 Reflectance spectra of $YZn_2Cu_3O_{6.5}$

The pellets of $YZn_2Cu_3O_{6.5}$ showed a high resistivity ($10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}$). In order to obtain the maximum photoresponse, the semiconductor electrode should

have a low resistivity. Therefore, before utilising the pellet of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ as a photoanode in the PEC cell, its resistivity must be lowered. This is achieved by sintering the pellets in a hydrogen atmosphere which causes oxygen deficiency and in turn enhances electrical conductivity. The resistivity was brought down to nearly $10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$. This value is rather high, but one has to maintain a mild reducing condition to prevent the formation of metallic Y and Zn.

The maximum power efficiency and the fill factor were calculated from I - V characteristic of PEC cell (Fig. 4). The photocurrents were measured at a different bias potentials. The fill factor and conversion efficiency were calculated to be 0.229 and 0.127% respectively. The low conversion efficiency due to the comparatively high band gap of the semiconductor⁶, the high internal resistance of the cell, polarisation and surface recombination centres on the electrode surface.

Fig. 4 I - V characteristics of a $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ photoanode.

It is concluded from the above studies that solar to electrical conversion efficiency of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ is quite low. However, attempts are being made to increase the conversion efficiency by using it, in the form of thin film or single crystal as photoanode in place of polycrystalline material.

Experimental

The ternary oxide, $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ was prepared by ceramic technique. Appropriate molar ratio mixture of

fine powders of Y_2O_3 , ZnO and CuO (A.R.) was ground using acetone (A.R.) for homogeneity with appropriate particle size. The mixture was then pressed to pellets (1.2 cm dia) which were fired at 1073 and 1223 K for 20 and 25 h⁷ respectively, after which the furnace was cooled slowly to room temperature at the rate of $1^\circ/\text{min}$. These pellets were again ground to fine powder and pressed to pellets and final firing was carried out at 1223 K for 20 h. Then these pellets were again crushed and used as material for the photoanode.

The chemical composition of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ was determined by estimating its metal content⁸. Its formation was further confirmed by X -ray diffraction (XRD) study using a Philips PW 1700 diffractometer with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation.

To characterise the material, its electrical resistivity in the range of 298–700 K was measured using a RM 160 MK III A megaohmmeter (BPL-India). A thin layer of silver paste was applied to clean faces of the pellet for providing good electrical contact⁹.

Diffuse reflectance spectra were scanned on a Varian DMS-80 spectrophotometer.

Pellets of $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ (thickness 3 mm) were prepared under a pressure of 1550 kg cm^{-2} and sintered in an atmosphere of hydrogen to enhance their electrical conductivity. Resistivity of the pellets was decreased to about $10^2 \Omega \text{ cm}$. The surface of the pellets was polished. The silver paste was applied to one surface of the pellet and fired at 573 K for 1 h. An ohmic contact between copper wire and silver coated surface was made and surface was covered with epoxy. This electrode acted as a photoanode.

A three-electrode PEC cell was designed using $\text{YZn}_2\text{Cu}_3\text{O}_{6.5}$ as the photoanode, platinum metal as the counter electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (Elico ER-70) as a reference electrode. The light source used was a 150 W tungsten-halogen lamp. The light intensity of 10 mW cm^{-2} was maintained at the plane of the electrode, having an effective working area of 1 cm^2 . In all PEC measurements, 0.1 M solution

of Ce^{3+}/Ce^{4+} was used as redox couple. Ammonium cerrous sulphate and ammonium ceric sulphate solutions were used to form the redox couple. The current-voltage characteristics of the cell have been studied, whose measurement procedure is described elsewhere¹⁰

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